

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT MODEL FOR TAP WATER QUALITY (USING THE CITY OF MINSK AS AN EXAMPLE)

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Abstract. *Monitoring of certain quality and safety indicators of tap water samples in districts of the city of Minsk was carried out. A model for comprehensive assessment of the quality of tap water samples was developed based on the calculation of weighted average indicators. To calculate the weight (significance) coefficients of individual quality indicators, an expert method was used, as well as the method of limit and nominal values. Based on the results obtained, a conclusion was made about the quality of tap water in Minsk.*

Keywords: *quality and safety of tap water, heavy metals, total, temporary and permanent hardness, total mineralization, hydrogen index, comprehensive quality assessment model.*

Introduction. Providing the population with drinking water is a priority task for every state, involving the creation and maintenance of centralized water supply systems, the regulation and control of water quality and safety indicators, the protection of water sources, and the introduction of purification technologies. Countries strive to provide full access to quality water, but at the same time, a significant part of the world's population still does not have access to safe drinking water.

According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the Republic of Belarus is among the top 20 countries in terms of population access to clean water. In terms of river water resources, the Republic of Belarus ranks fourth in Europe after Norway, the United Kingdom, and Poland. According to the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environmental Protection, the water resource availability index in the Republic of Belarus is at the European average of 6.2 thousand m³ per capita per year, which is significantly higher than in some neighboring countries. More than 40% of water is used for domestic and drinking purposes [1].

All Central Asian republics are among the world leaders in per capita water consumption. According to Worldometers, Turkmenistan tops this ranking with a daily consumption of 15,445 liters per capita. Uzbekistan ranks fourth in the ranking with an average consumption of 4,754 liters, while Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan rank fifth and sixth with consumption of 4,460 and 4,153 liters per capita, respectively. Russia, with an average consumption of 1,306 liters, ranks 67th, and Belarus ranks 126th in this ranking (daily consumption is 419 liters per capita) [2,11].

Every year, the Center for Environmental Policy and Law at Yale University compiles a

ranking of the world's most environmentally friendly countries, according to which Belarus ranked 39th in terms of drinking water quality in 2024 and 32nd out of 180 countries in terms of environmental performance. The top ten countries with the safest drinking water in the Environmental Policy Center's ranking include Finland, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, the United States, Norway, and Luxembourg [3].

A national environmental monitoring system has been established in the Republic of Belarus. Particular attention is paid to monitoring the safety indicators of surface and groundwater. Over the past 20 years, there has been a 7.8-fold reduction in the discharge of water exceeding permissible standards. Water from artesian sources (wells) is considered the cleanest, as its deep location prevents it from being contaminated by inorganic and organic substances, as well as microorganisms.

A large-scale project has been implemented in Minsk, the capital of the Republic of Belarus, thanks to which all consumers have access to water from underground sources. Water is supplied by 15 water intakes and 386 artesian wells, with a total length of water supply networks exceeding 3,000 km. City residents can check out the results of lab tests of water in their homes at specific addresses online on the Minskvodokanal website [4]. The quality and safety of water from underground sources is checked before it is supplied to the city's distribution network. In functioning centralized domestic and drinking water supply systems, the system owner ensures that laboratory tests of water are carried out at least once a year, including tests for physiological adequacy (total mineralization, hardness, macro- and microelement content, ensuring disease prevention by eliminating deficiencies in biologically essential elements) before the drinking water enters the distribution network. At the same time, it should be noted that the quality of water in a particular room is influenced by a number of additional factors, such as the age of the building, the condition of internal pipelines and supply lines, as well as the material from which the pipes and taps are made. Thus, the quality and safety indicators of water supplied to a residential building from an artesian source may vary from apartment to apartment.

The aim of this work is to develop a model for comprehensive assessment of tap water quality based on monitoring certain quality and safety indicators in order to determine (predict) possible and priority areas of its use (using the city of Minsk as an example). The assessment of tap water quality was based on experimental results obtained by determining the concentration of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cu) in tap water samples taken in various areas of Minsk, as well as the hydrogen index (pH), total mineralization, total, temporary, and permanent hardness indicators.

The Republic of Belarus has sanitary rules and regulations governing the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of inorganic and organic substances in water, as well as standards for generalized water quality indicators (Table 1) [5].

Table 1. Standards for certain generalized indicators and chemical substances in drinking water

<i>Indicator name</i>	<i>Unit of measurement</i>	<i>Standards(maximum permissible concentrations(MPC) no more than</i>
Hydrogen index	pH units	within 6–9
Total mineralization	mg/dm ³	1000
Total haedness	mmol/dm ³	7,0

Cadmium (Cd, total)	mg/dm ³	0,001
Copper (Cu, total)	mg/dm ³	1,0
Lead (Pb, total)	mg/dm ³	0,03
Zinc (Zn ²⁺)	mg/dm ³	5,0

Research methodology. The determination of zinc, cadmium, lead, and copper when they are present together was carried out using the inversion voltammetry method on an ABA-3 voltammetric analyzer equipped with a rotating carbon steel indicator electrode, a silver chloride reference electrode, and a platinum auxiliary electrode. The conditions for recording voltammetric curves when determining heavy metals were established in the course of numerous studies [6, 7]: electrochemical cleaning of the carbon-based indicator electrode at a potential of +0.45 V for 20 s; accumulation of Zn, Cd, Pb, and Cu at a potential of -1.40 V for 60 s; stabilization of the solution at a potential of -1.35 V for 10 s; potential sweep at a rate of 0.50 V/s in the potential range from -1.35 V to +0.45 V. A 0.35 mol/dm³ aqueous solution of formic acid was used as the background. The heavy metal content in mineral waters was calculated based on the difference between the volt-ampere curves of the sample and the background, the sample with the addition of a standard solution, and the background using a specialized computer program analyzer. Standard metal solutions were prepared based on State Standard Samples (SSS).

The total mineralization of water was determined using an express conductometric method with a HANNA HI 8734 conductometer-salinity meter. The conductometer-salinity meter sensor, thoroughly washed with distilled water and dried with filter paper, was immersed in tap water samples, and after the instrument readings stabilized, the total mineralization was recorded.

The hydrogen index was measured using a pH-150M pH meter with a glass indicator electrode, pre-calibrated using three buffer solutions with pH values of 4.01, 6.80, and 9.18, prepared from standard titrants. The device readings were taken no earlier than one minute after immersing the electrodes in the water being measured [6].

The determination of total, temporary, and permanent hardness was carried out using a titrimetric method [8]. The total hardness of water was determined by titrating water with a solution of trilon B (complexon III), capable of forming poorly dissociated complex compounds with magnesium and calcium ions. Temporary hardness, caused by the content of hydrocarbonates Ca(HCO₃)₂, Mg(HCO₃)₂, Fe(HCO₃)₂, was determined by titrating water with hydrochloric acid solution, whereby the hydrocarbonates dissolved in water react quantitatively with hydrochloric acid. The permanent hardness of water, which is determined by the presence of calcium and magnesium sulfates and chlorides CaSO₄, MgSO₄, CaCl₂, MgCl₂ in water, was calculated as the difference between the total and temporary hardness.

Research results. The results of testing tap water samples collected in nine districts of Minsk are presented in Table 2.

Excessive zinc content was detected in a tap water sample taken in the Leninsky district, where the concentration was 14.06 mg/dm³, which is 2.8 times higher than the maximum permissible value. This may be due to contamination during water transportation through old metal or galvanized pipes. The cadmium concentration in some samples is at the MPC level. All tested tap water samples comply with the established standards for lead and copper content. Overall, drinking water in Minsk complies with hygiene standards, but local exceedances of zinc require

regular monitoring and modernization of water supply networks and plumbing equipment in specific buildings and premises.

Table 2. Results of testing tap water samples in Minsk

<i>Sampling area (Minsk)</i>	<i>Metal content, mg/dm³</i>				<i>pH</i>	<i>Hardness, mmol/ dm³</i>			<i>Total mineralization, mg/dm³</i>
	<i>Zn</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Pb</i>	<i>Cu</i>		<i>total</i>	<i>temporar</i>	<i>permane</i>	
Oktyabrsky (dormitory No. 1)	1,2	0,0010	0,006	0,252	7,35	5,7 5	5,0 0	0,7 5	250
Leninsky (academic building)	14,0	0,0010	0,015	0,204	7,52	5,6 0	5,2 5	0,3 5	277
Centralny (residential apartment)	1,6	0,0010	0,007	0,39	7,56	6,2 5	4,6 3	1,6 2	313
Moskovsky (dormitory No. 9)	4,9	0,0010	0,005	0,974	7,58	5,1 3	5,0 0	0,1 3	225
Zavodskoy (educational building)	1,6	0,0002	0,005	0,308	7,80	4,3 5	3,7 5	0,6 0	172
Sovietsky (dormitory No. 2)	1,7	0,0004	0,004	0,238	7,47	6,1 5	4,2 0	1,9 5	256
Frunzensky(residential apartment)	2,2	0,0008	0,007	0,22	7,74	5,2 5	4,9 0	0,3 5	214
Pervomaisky (library)	2,1	0,0010	0,014	0,886	6,68	5,1 0	4,3 0	0,8 0	264
Partizansky (residential apartment)	4,5	0,0009	0,008	0,468	7,01	4,9 5	4,7 5	0,2 0	234
Regulated value	5,0	0,001	0,03	1,0	6-9	7	-	-	1000

In terms of hydrogen content, all tested tap water samples comply with established standards. The pH of the water samples ranges from 6.68 to 7.80.

All tap water samples from nine districts of Minsk fully comply with established sanitary and hygienic standards in terms of both total mineralization and total hardness. The lowest values of the regulated indicators of total mineralization and total hardness were recorded in the Zavodsky district (172 mg/dm³; 4.35 mmol/dm³), and the highest in the Central district (313 ml/dm³, 6.26 mmol/dm³). The spread between the minimum and maximum values is: for total mineralization – 141 mg/dm³, for total hardness – 1.9 mmol/dm³. It should be noted that the obtained values of the standardized water quality indicators correlate with each other (the higher the value of the total mineralization of a water sample, the higher its hardness), which is explained by the chemical composition of groundwater – the main salt components are calcium and magnesium compounds, which determine the hardness of water.

The results obtained allowed us to make a preliminary conclusion that water from underground sources used for centralized water supply in Minsk is generally safe for health and

suitable for domestic use. In some cases, excessive zinc content is most likely due to the technical condition, degree of wear and tear, and length of operation of the water supply networks and plumbing equipment of a particular building or even a room.

At the same time, climate change increases the value of groundwater as the main source of drinking water supply, which requires an assessment of the feasibility of providing all subscribers with drinking-quality water from underground sources of drinking water supply and the development of a technical water supply system. The qualitative composition of groundwater, including mineral water, and its reserves allow, in addition to meeting economic and drinking needs, the use of such water for medical (resort, health) purposes, as well as export through bottling [9]. Thus, in order to increase the efficiency of water resource use, it is necessary to define criteria and develop an algorithm for their assessment.

Methodology for assessing the quality of tap water. As part of the study, a model for assessing the quality of tap water was developed, allowing for the values of all experimentally established individual quality and safety indicators to be taken into account, as well as their significance for calculating a comprehensive indicator. The value of the comprehensive indicator obtained as a result of the calculation will, in turn, allow conclusions to be drawn about the quality level of the tap water samples studied in order to select priority and possible ways of its further use.

A comprehensive comparative assessment was carried out using the weighted arithmetic mean (WAM), which was calculated using formula (1):

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^n q_i \times \alpha_i \quad (1),$$

where α_i – is the weight coefficient of the i -th quality indicator, q_i – the relative value of the i -th unit quality indicator of the evaluated product [10].

The relative value of the quality indicator is calculated using formula (2):

$$q_i = \frac{p_{ibase.}}{p_i} \quad (2),$$

where p_i – is the absolute value of the i -th quality indicator of the evaluated tap water sample;

$p_{ibase.}$ – is the absolute value of the i -th quality indicator of the reference tap water sample (the values of the quality indicators of the reference sample were taken from the regulated values of tap water quality and safety indicators presented in Table 1); n is the number of quality indicators used to assess the quality of tap water. Thus, if q_i is greater than 1, then the tap water sample being evaluated exceeds the base sample in terms of this indicator; if it is less than 1, then the sample being evaluated is worse than the base sample (in this case, it does not meet the regulated requirements).

Results of the assessment of the quality of tap water. The results of the calculation of the relative values of the quality indicators q_i are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The results of calculating the relative values of quality indicators q_i

Sampling area (Minsk)	Metal content, mg/dm ³				pH	Hardness, mmol/ dm ³			Total mineralization
	Zn	Cd	Pb	Cu		total	temporary	permanent	
	relative values of quality indicators q_i								
Октябрьский (общежитие №1)	4,20	1,00	5,15	3,97	1,22	1,22	1,00	2,67	4,00
Oktyabrsky (dormitory No. 1)	0,36	1,00	2,00	4,90	1,20	1,25	0,95	5,71	3,61
Leninsky (academic building)	3,12	1,00	4,50	2,56	1,19	1,12	1,08	1,23	3,19
Centralny (residential apartment)	1,02	1,00	5,66	1,03	1,19	1,37	1,00	16,00	4,44
Moskovsky (dormitory No. 9)	3,03	5,00	5,49	3,25	1,15	1,61	1,33	3,33	5,81
Zavodskoy (educational building)	2,88	2,50	6,73	4,20	1,21	1,14	1,19	1,03	3,91
Sovietsky (dormitory No. 2)	2,23	1,25	4,45	4,55	1,16	1,33	1,02	5,71	4,67
Frunzensky (residential apartment)	2,38	1,00	2,20	1,13	1,35	1,37	1,16	2,50	3,79
Pervomaisky (library)	1,11	1,11	3,75	2,14	1,28	1,41	1,05	10,00	4,27
Partizansky (residential apartment)									

As can be seen from the table, the vast majority of the relative values of water sample quality indicators $q_i > 1$, this indicates that according to these quality indicators, the studied samples not only meet the requirements of the standard, but also exceed the quality indicators of the base sample, for which a conditional water sample with numerical values of quality indicators equal to the maximum permissible values was adopted in this work.

The weighting coefficients of individual quality indicators are determined by the method of maximum and nominal values based on the use of known maximum permissible values of quality indicators. The values from which the permissible deviations are calculated are used as nominal values.

Weighting factors α_i . The quality indicators for the average weighted arithmetic complex indicator are calculated using the formula (3):

$$\alpha_i = \frac{P_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{P_i}{|P_{iH} - P_{iN}|}} \quad (3),$$

where P_{iN} – the ultimate absolute value of the quality indicator; P_{iH} – the nominal absolute value of the quality indicator (the average value of the set range for a specific quality indicator). The limit values and nominal values of the quality and safety of tap water are shown in Table 3.

All calculations are performed in the Exel program. The obtained values of the weighting coefficients (significance) of individual quality indicators and the values of complex weighted arithmetic averages of the quality of tap water samples are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. The values of the weighting coefficients of individual quality indicators and complex weighted arithmetic averages of the quality of tap water samples

Sampling area (Minsk)	Metal content, mg/dm ³				pH	Hardness, mmol/ dm ³			Total mineralization	WA A
	Zn	Cd	Pb	Cu		total	temporary	permanent		
	the coefficient of weighting (significance)									
Октябрьский (общежитие №1)	0,036	0,152	0,029	0,038	0,372	0,125	0,152	0,057	0,038	1,672
Oktyabrsky (dormitory No. 1)	0,302	0,107	0,054	0,022	0,269	0,086	0,113	0,019	0,030	1,180
Leninsky (academic building)	0,043	0,135	0,030	0,053	0,341	0,121	0,125	0,110	0,042	1,487
Centralny (residential apartment)	0,128	0,130	0,023	0,127	0,329	0,095	0,130	0,008	0,029	1,433
Moskovsky (dormitory No. 9)	0,060	0,037	0,033	0,056	0,476	0,114	0,137	0,055	0,031	2,014
Zavodskoy (educational building)	0,053	0,061	0,023	0,036	0,379	0,134	0,128	0,148	0,039	1,674
Sovietsky (dormitory No. 2)	0,070	0,125	0,035	0,034	0,404	0,117	0,153	0,027	0,033	1,721
Frunzensky(residenti al apartment)	0,058	0,138	0,063	0,122	0,308	0,101	0,119	0,055	0,036	1,519
Pervomaisky (library)	0,132	0,131	0,039	0,068	0,340	0,103	0,138	0,015	0,034	1,602
Limit value	5,0	0,001	0,03	1,0	6-9	7	5	2	1,0	
Nominal value	2,5	0,0005	0,015	0,5	7,5	3,5	2,5	1	0,5	

Based on the obtained values of complex weighted arithmetic averages of quality indicators, it can be concluded that among the studied samples, the best quality level is a sample of tap water from the Zavodsky district of Minsk (U=2.014), and the lowest is a sample of water taken in the Leninsky district of Minsk (U=1.180). In terms of quality, the best sample is almost 2 times higher than the sample with the lowest CBA value. It should be noted that the highest zinc content exceeding the regulated value was found in the Leninsky district water sample, but the sample was not excluded from the calculations, since zinc belongs to trace elements. The sample

of tap water in the Zavodsky district demonstrated the lowest values of the total hardness index (4.35 mmol/dm³) and can be classified as soft.

Conclusions.

1. Based on the experimental results obtained for determining the concentration of heavy metals (Zn, Pb, Cd, Cu) in tap water samples taken in nine districts of Minsk, as well as the hydrogen index (pH), indicators of total mineralization, total, temporary and permanent hardness, it can be concluded that water from underground sources used for centralized water supply in Minsk, it is generally safe for health and favorable for domestic use.

2. In some cases, the excess metal content in tap water may most likely be due to the technical condition, degree of wear and duration of operation of water supply networks and plumbing equipment of a particular building or even premises.

3. A model for assessing the quality of tap water has been developed by calculating a weighted arithmetic average, which allows taking into account the values of all experimentally determined single indicators of quality and safety. The method of limit values and nominal values is used to calculate the weighting coefficients of individual indicators of the quality and safety of tap water.

4. Based on the obtained values of complex weighted arithmetic averages of quality, it is concluded that among the studied samples, the best quality level is a sample of tap water from the Zavodsky district of Minsk (U=2.014), and the lowest is a sample of water taken in the Leninsky district of Minsk (U=1.180). Tap water from the Zavodsky district of Minsk can be recommended for export by bottling (subject to compliance with the requirements for all regulated indicators).

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